

PROPENSITY SCORE ANALYSIS TO KNOW THE EFFECT OF EXCLUSIVE BREASTFEEDING ON UNDER-FIVE CHILDREN PNEUMONIA

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Abstract

Pneumonia is the dominant cause of under-five children mortality other than diarrhea (GKIA, 2016). Based on Profil Kesehatan Surabaya (2017) that the highest case of pneumonia in Surabaya on 2016 is in the Puskesmas Sememi. Exclusive breastfeeding is one factor that can prevent the occurrence of under-five children pneumonia. Propensity score matching (PSM) as a method that can minimize the influence of variables suspected as confounding. The goal of this study is to analyze the use of PSM method to determine the effect of exclusive breastfeeding on under-five children pneumonia case at Puskesmas Sememi Surabaya by controlling variables considered confounding. The type of research used is cross-sectional. The samples is 61 respondents, under-five children of pneumonia was taken by systematic random sampling technique. The method used by conducting interviews using questionnaires and secondary data in Puskesmas Sememi. The results showed the covariate equilibrium test (p -value = 0.280). The result of the covariate equilibrium test after PSM shows that the covariate has no effect which means it has been controlled. Exclusive breastfeeding affects the case of under-five children pneumonia with covariates of nutritional status, maternal employment, mother's education, birth weight, and basic immunization status of under-five children.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Propensity score is a statistical method that develops the estimated effect of treatment with non-experimental or observational data. The benefits of propensity score in equalization, stratification, and weighting are some of the dimensions reduction.^[1] There are several types of propensity scores, one of them is propensity score matching. Propensity score matching can be used as a more complex method subtly and combines two conventional methods, namely regression and matching.^[1] The use of a propensity score matching test is in the case of an estimated confounding variable. Health is one indicator of the welfare of a country. Indonesia has many health problems that need attention, one of them is the pneumonia case of children under-five. Based on information released by the Pusat Komunikasi Publik, Sekretariat Jenderal Departemen Kesehatan, more than 2 million children under five die from pneumonia from 9 million under-five deaths every year in the world. Every minute there are four under-five children dead and one of the deaths is due to pneumonia.^[2]

Under-five mortality is dominated by pneumonia and diarrhea which is included in one of the preventable infectious diseases.^[3] Under-five mortality in 2015 was caused by pneumonia estimated at 922,000 children under five in the world.^[4]

Figure 1. Health Centers that Have the Most Number of Pneumonia Cases in Surabaya in 2016. Source: Profil Kesehatan Surabaya (2017)

Pneumonia cases of under-five children found and treated in Surabaya in 2016 were 3.925 under-five children. Based on Figure 1 it can be seen that the highest number of cases of pneumonia in under-five children in Surabaya, namely the Puskesmas Sememi is 281 under-five children. The number of cases of toddler pneumonia in Puskesmas Sememi 2016 is suitable for use in the propensity score matching test due to matching that requires variable selection. Propensity score matching begins with an estimate of propensity score and is followed by a selection of matching.^[5] In addition, this study wanted to see the effect of exclusive breastfeeding by controlling variables suspected of being disruptors, namely the mother's last education, maternal work, basic immunization status, nutritional status, and birth weight. The control of potential confounding variables is suitable to apply propensity score matching.

2. METHOD

The type of research used is analytic study with cross-sectional design. The population is all children under-five who have pneumonia in the month of July-December 2017 in the work area of Puskesmas Sememi in the amount of 108 under-five children. Sampling was carried out with a systematic random sampling technique that was 61 samples.

3. RESULTS

This study requires maternal respondents who have children under-five years to find out the variables needed in the study, namely birth weight, basic immunization status, nutritional status, maternal occupation, mother's education level, and exclusive breastfeeding.

Table 1. Number of Under-five children Based on Pneumonia Status at Puskesmas Sememi in July-December 2017

Pneumonia (Y)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Severe	16	26,2
Mild	45	73,8
Total	139	100,0

Table 1 describes the percentage of children under-five with severe pneumonia cases in under-five children by 26.2% and with cases of mild pneumonia in infants by 73.8%. This shows that the majority of respondents in Puskesmas Sememi have children with mild pneumonia cases.

Table 2. Crosstabulation between Toddler Pneumonia and Toddler Nutrition Status

Nutritional Status	Toddler Pneumonia Status		Total
	Mild	Severe	
Abnormal	9 (60,0%)	6 (40,0%)	15 (100%)
Normal	36 (78,3%)	10 (21,7%)	46 (100%)

Table 2 provides information that children with severe pneumonia have abnormal nutritional status of 40%, greater than having normal nutritional status of 21.7%.

Table 3. Crosstabulation between Toddler Pneumonia and Maternal Occupation

Work	Toddler Pneumonia Status		Total
	Mild	Severe	
Yes	21 (67,7%)	10 (32,3%)	31 (100%)
No	24 (80,0%)	6 (20,0%)	30 (100%)

Table 3 provides information that under-five children with severe pneumonia had a working mother of 32.3%, greater than having a mother who did not work at 20%.

Table 4. Crosstabulation between Toddler Pneumonia and Mother's Education Level

Mother's Education Level	Toddler Pneumonia Status		Total
	Mild	Severe	
Low	14 (70,0%)	6 (30,0%)	20 (100%)
High	31 (75,6%)	10 (24,4%)	41 (100%)

Table 4 provides information that under-five children with severe pneumonia had a low educated mother at 30%, greater than 24.4% had a highly educated mother.

Table 5. Crosstabulation between Toddler Pneumonia and Birth Weight

Birth Weight	Toddler Pneumonia Status		Total
	Mild	Severe	
Low	3 (50,0%)	3 (50,0%)	6 (100%)
Not low	42 (76,4%)	13 (23,6%)	55 (100%)

Table 5 provides information that infants with severe pneumonia have a LBW status of 50%, greater than having a non-LBW status of 23.6%.

Table 6. Crosstabulation between Toddler Pneumonia and Basic Immunization Status

Basic Immunization	Toddler Pneumonia Status		Total
	Mild	Severe	
Not complete	4 (44,4%)	5 (55,6%)	9 (100%)
Complete	41 (78,8%)	16 (21,2%)	52 (100%)

Table 6 provides information that children with severe pneumonia have incomplete basic immunization status of 55.6%, greater than having a complete basic immunization status of 21.2%.

Table 7. Crosstabulation between Toddler Pneumonia and Exclusive Breastfeeding

Exclusive Breastfeeding	Toddler Pneumonia Status		Total
	Mild	Severe	
No	20 (60,6%)	13 (39,4%)	33 (100%)
Yes	25 (89,3%)	3 (10,7%)	28 (100%)

Table 7 provides information that under-five children with severe pneumonia were given non-exclusive breastfeeding at 39.4%, greater than those who were given exclusive breastfeeding at 10.7%. The effect of exclusive breastfeeding on pneumonia cases on under-five children needs to be known to compare the difference in magnitude of influence between pre and post propensity score matching.

Table 8. Effect of Exclusive Breastfeeding on Cases Of Underfive Pneumonia Pre and Post PSM

Indicator	Pre PSM	Post PSM
<i>p-value</i>	0,017	0,033
Exp (B)	5,417	6,375
B	1,689	1,852
Opportunity	0,394	0,429

Based on Table 8, the effect of exclusive breastfeeding on cases of pneumonia under-five post PSM (Exp (B) = 6,375) was greater than pre PSM (Exp (B) = 5,417). This is due to the control of variables that are considered confounding, namely maternal work, maternal's education level, birth weight, nutritional status, and basic immunization status.

4. DISCUSSION

Under-five children who have nutritional status are less at risk of pneumonia by 6.52 times compared to under-five children who have good nutritional status.^[6] There is significant association between nutritional status and the incidence of pneumonia.^[7]

Under-five children who have severe pneumonia have the majority of working mothers. Mothers of under-five children who work have less time to care for their children so the risk of

having children under-five experience severe cases of pneumonia. Under-five children whose mothers worked were at risk of developing pneumonia 2 times compared to under-five children whose mothers did not work (C.I. 95%: OR = 1.39-3.12).^[8]

Under-five children with severe pneumonia mostly have the last low level educated mothers. Children under-five whose mothers have a low level education are at risk of developing pneumonia 4 times compared to under-five children whose mothers are highly educated level.^[8]

Under-five children who have severe pneumonia have a majority of LBW status. The results of statistical tests indicate that children under five born with LBW are at risk of experiencing pneumonia by 8.9 times compared to children under-five with normal birth weight^[9]

Under-five children with severe pneumonia mostly have incomplete basic immunization status. That children under-five with incomplete immunization status (not measles immunization) are at risk of developing 1.6 times pneumonia compared to children under-five with complete immunization status. (C.I. 95%: OR = 1.08-2.46).^[8] Immunization is the provision of immunity so that the body is resistant to diseases that are endemic, the results of statistical tests indicate that immunization has a significant effect on the incidence of pneumonia of children under-five.^[10]

Exclusive breastfeeding is significantly associated with the incidence of under-five pneumonia (OR = 1.994).^[8] Under-five children who are given non-exclusive breastfeeding have a risk of pneumonia as much as 3.6 times greater than under-five children who are given exclusive breastfeeding.^[11]

Under-five children who were given exclusive breastfeeding were at 4.47 times the risk of pneumonia compared to under-five children who were exclusively breastfed.^[6] Breast milk contains substances needed by babies such as protein, sugar, fat, and calcium with appropriate levels. Babies who consume breast milk exclusively rarely experience upper tract infections in the first year of birth.^[12]

Breast milk contains colostrum as a potential antibody because it contains protein to maintain the body's immune power and kill germs effectively in high amounts. The first day until the fourth day colostrum is yellowish. The fourth day until the tenth day breast milk contains less immunoglobulin, protein, and lactose than colostrum but higher fat and calories with whiter milk. Therefore, breast milk can play a role in reducing the risk of a baby's disease.^[13]

The chance of a pneumonia case toddler will experience severe pneumonia cases before and after the propensity score matching method is not much different. This is caused by variations in covariates that are not too large. The differences that are not too large are caused by variations in covariate variables, especially exposed groups are not too large. In addition, the difference that is not too large is caused also by the influence of small confounding variables.^[14]

5. CONCLUSION

Exclusive breastfeeding affects cases of pneumonia of children under-five with nutritional status covariates, maternal occupation, maternal's education level, birth weight, and basic immunization status of children under-five. There needs to be a policy to increase exclusive breastfeeding by regulating exclusive breastfeeding time, especially for working mothers so that pneumonia cases can be prevented and their impact minimized, especially in the Puskesmas Sememi Surabaya.

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